

Comparative Analysis of Selected Heavy Metals and Trace Elements Content in Hair Dyes Products at Sudanese Market and Their Health Implications

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ABSTRACT: Heavy metals are naturally occurring elements that have a high atomic weight. They have been included in many industrial, domestic, medical and agricultural applications. This raised concerns over their health implications and the environment. The present study was conducted in Khartoum state for females utilizing commercial hair dye, aimed to study health implications of selected heavy metals and trace elements in commercially available hair dyes. The main aim of the present research work refers to the high degree of toxicity of some heavy metals, such as cadmium, mercury, lead and others, that are of public health significance. These health implications depend on various factors such as, type of chemical materials, route of exposure, age, gender, nutritional status, etc. In this context, the researcher compared the findings related to the present studied trace elements and heavy metals with other studies in the literature. 313 participants participating in this study, ages between less than 20 years and more than 40 years. Most of them of university education level. Many of participants have gray hair. The results of this study showed the presence of lead, copper, chromium, nickel and cadmium in all of the analyzed hair dye samples. The pure mineral dyes have higher concentrations of the heavy metals than the synthetic dyes studied. Long term and frequent use of these products polluted with such heavy metals should be avoided. They may cause slow release of metals into the human body and may pose serious health risk to their users. Regulatory agencies saddled with maintaining standard of products should regularly monitor these products for long-term health benefits of the users. Heavy metals of Cd, Pb, Cu, Hg Cr and Ni, were found in all hair dye samples tested. Heavy metals in blood samples of participants cause many symptoms and disease after using hair dyes. The most concentrated heavy metals and trace elements (i.e. Pb, Cd, Mn, Hg, Cu and Ni) in blood samples of participants were tested. Results clarified that the high concentration represented for LEAD in blood samples by FLAME AAS and GF AAS. The results also showed the socio demographic factors for using hair dyes, and factors behind using synthetic hair dyes instead of natural hair dyes. Many studies and researches that focused on the topic of the current study confirmed the presence of heavy metals in the cosmetics of poetry of hair dyes and different types of henna. Some women differ in the presence of heavy metals in their vital components, such as hair and blood, depending on their use of cosmetics and the number of times used.

KEY WORDS: Heavy metals; lead, selenium, mercury, cadmium, human exposure; marketed hair dyes; toxicity; international standards; CT number, Computed Tomography,

1.1Background: Heavy metals are the most serious threat to human health. These metals have been extensively researched, and their effects on human health are regularly reviewed by international bodies such as the World Health Organization (WHO). Heavy metal exposure continues to occur despite the fact that several adverse health effects of heavy metals have been known for a long time. Toxic elements, even at a low concentration, can be extremely harmful if consumed for an extended period of time[1]. Heavy metals are widely available in our environment, making it difficult to avoid their presence and impact on the human body. Some heavy metals are necessary for the human body, but only in small amounts. Heavy metals are known to be present in many cosmetic products, including hair dyes, which can enter the body through the skin and root of the hair. As a result, if they are present in high concentrations in the body, they can cause a variety of health problems. It is thus more important to determine the content of heavy metals in hair dyes by using different types made by different manufacturers. The complexity of commercial hair dye formulas, with dozens of components and formulas that differ between manufacturers, In general, hair dyes[2].

Health is most renowned for people who are concerned about their health, and their children's and other family members health, i.e. providing "healthy home and living", namely, how to fight against premature aging, increase energy, prevent disease and accidents, and live longer and happier by reducing and avoiding their exposure to toxins and environmental hazards found in the home, and other locations (and activities) in which they spend most of their life. Heavy metals are a term that covers a group of elements with similar chemical properties. Some of them, including copper (Cu), iron (Fe), zinc (Zn), magnesium (Mg) play an important role in human organism and are called essential metals, while others like lead (Pb) and mercury (Hg) are not known as being useful for our health, or more precisely they are toxic. High concentrations of heavy metals to an alarming level may cause health problems [1]. Hair coloring, or hair dyeing, is the practice of changing the hair color. The main reasons for this are cosmetic: to cover gray or white hair, to change to a color regarded as more fashionable or desirable, or to restore the original hair color after it has been discolored by hairdressing processes or sun bleaching. Hair coloring could be done professionally by a hairdresser or independently at home. The dyeing of hair is an ancient art that involves treatment of the hair with various chemical compounds and dyes obtained from plants [3]. In the 1661 book Eighteen Books of the Secrets of Art & Nature, various methods of coloring hair black, gold, green, red, yellow, and white were explained [4]. The development of synthetic dyes for hair was traced since the 1860s discovery of the reactivity of para-phenylenediamine (PPD) with air [5]. Eugène Schueller, the founder of L'Oréal, is recognized for creating the first synthetic hair dye in 1907 [6]. In 1947 the German cosmetics firm Schwarzkopf launched the first home color product [7]. Hair dyeing is now a multibillion-dollar industry that involves the use of both plant-derived and synthetic dyes [8]. detergent may sometimes work as may moist cigarette ash rubbed into the stained area [9].

1.2. Problem statement: Some of the heavy metals in hair coloring agents may include lead, mercury, silver, bismuth, and arsenic causes of hair dye poisoning [10]. There are number of allergic and kidney damage and dyspnea cases appear in those women who use hair dyes.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials:

2.1.1. Samples:

2.1.1.1. Hair dyes samples: Eleven types of black hair dyes of major brands were purchased from retail shops in Khartoum (Sudan) at the time of study (March-August 2021, table 2-1).

2.1.1.2 : Blood Samples: The blood samples were collected from 19 participant women inside Khartoum.

2.2.2.1. Hair dyes samples:

2.2.2.1.1. Samples preparation for analysis of presence of Pb ,Cd , Cu , Ni , Mn in marketed hair dyes : 5 gm of sample was weighed in a tall beaker, 30 ml of conc. Hydrochloric acid and 10 ml of nitric acid were added, the beakers were covered with a glass watch , and then the contents were boiled on a sand bath for 30 min until dry. After that little more of nitric acid was added and heated until dry again.

Then cooled, and 40 ml of hydrochloric acid : water (1:20) were added, heated to dissolve and cooled.

The extracts were made up to volume 200 ml , filtered and used for AAS determinations.

2.2.2.1.2. Hair dyes preparation for determination of mercury (Hg) :

The homogenized sample was precisely weighed (0.500) gm and placed at the bottom as sample digestion flask .then 1 ml of distilled water was added followed by 2 ml of HNO₃: HClO₄ (1:1), then 5 ml of conc.H₂SO₄ were added , the content were shaken carefully and heated on a hot plate at 220°C as digestion temperature for 30 min , allowed to cool, diluted with distilled water and filtered by using whattman filter papers 42, washed to made up volume of 50 ml and mixed well , a blank solution was made with same procedure without adding the sample [10]. The resulting solution was used for AAS determination of various metal analyses. According to safety rules in chemical laboratory, this procedure was carried out in fume hood. Concentration of Pb, Cd, Ni , Mn and Cu will determined in ppm in hair dyes samples using AAS after sample preparation by acid digestion. Preparation of standard calibration curves were plotted for each element.[10].

2.2.2.2. Blood samples:

2.2.2.2.1. Study design: The study is cross sectional institutional and community based study.

2.2.2.2.2: Study area and setting: some of our participants women are married female live in their house in Khartoum state. Most of the participant women are worker as henna drawer some of them work in beauty centers and the remainders work in their homes.

In the beauty center also there are hair dying, sauna, hair dressing and all types of body care. Those beauty centers are under the auspices of the local authorities and tax official.

2.3. Data collection (Methods and tools):

2.3.1. Methods:

2.3.1.1. Questionnaire: A cross-sectional survey (Questionnaire written in Arabic chosen from previous study and modified to be suitable with this study was employed to assess the knowledge, attitude and practice (KAP) of using hair dyes contain pretested – structural organized closed questions and closed and open questions[11]. A cross-sectional survey (questionnaire written in Arabic) was employed to assess the knowledge, attitude and practice (KAP) of using hair dyes.

2.3.1.2. Data sheet of AAS analysis of hair dyes from The Criminal Evidences Investigations laboratory Khartoum. The data sheet is pretested – organized structural has closed question.

2.3.1.3. Lab or blood investigation with data sheet from The Criminal Evidences Investigations laboratory Khartoum.

2.3.2. Data analysis: By SPSS version: 28

Test: Determination of mean , SD , MAX value ,MIN value, Result in form of charts and graphs. The data collected through the questionnaire will statistically be analyzed using SPSS program (Statistical Package for Social Sciences).

2.3.3.1. Blood sample collection: Criteria of selection of blood samples are cited below. The age was between 18-50yrs. Working duration period of exposure was noted. Freshly collected blood samples were analyzed. All blood samples followed by aseptic condition. Amount of blood sample was 5ml from forearm and kept in median cubital vein. Samples were kept into the anticoagulated Vacutainer samples were collected from different places of Khartoum state mostly from hair dyes drawer in September 2022 . Blood were collected into phlebotomist from median cubital vein with sterilized disposable syringe . Ant coagulant was added for whole blood analysis and place in refrigerator for 9 samples determined by GFAAS and 10 samples were centrifuged for plasma determination by FAAS [12].

2.3.3.2. Physical parameters determination of blood: Examination includes quantity of blood, age of blood taker, marital status, chronic disease and contact time period of heavy metal acquisition. Quantity of blood was equal for all samples .All samples were collected at same cite of persons. A targeted physical exam was performed, including measurement of height and weight. Finally, study staff administered an environmental questionnaire identifying possible sources of exposure to heavy metals [12].

2.3.3.4. Preparation of blood samples :

2.3.3.4.1. For whole blood analysis : In this work wet digestion were used for optimization. Wet digestion includes decomposition by acids carried out on hotplate. Same procedure can also be done in aluminum heating block, closed vessels at high P, with thermal heating. Took 5ml of sample in 100 ml volumetric flask, followed by adding 10ml of nitric acid. Put it on hot plate for round about 2hr and allowed temperature to increase 160C. Continued boiling regularly for two hour to reduce volume .Filtration applied to samples by filter discs which were grade of 389 and blood samples kept allowed to cool. After completion of digestion add 10ml of hydrogen peroxide. At the end dilute it up to 50ml and filtered. Important parameters under investigation were acids volume, digestion time period, pre digestion period, temperature and also the amount of samples [12].

2.3.3.4.2. For plasma analysis :Blood sample ppn. for flame AAS : 5MLS of anticoagulant whole blood was pipetted into 10 ml volumetric flask , 1ml of 10% TX and 1 ml of 2% APDC were added in order, the mixture was agitated well after each step , 1ml of MIBK(water saturated) was added and was shaken well for 5 min , 1 ml of deionized water was added .blood sample was centrifuged at about 700 g for 10 min .

2.3.3.4.3. Sample and standard solution preparation for analysis: Blood samples were prepared in two steps. Preparation of standards (Cu, Cd ,pb) was done followed by wet digestion and analysis of HM. Standards of different concentration for heavy metals prepared from SS (standard solution). There was correlation in standard and signal. Working standard produced by liquefy solution. After signal analysis graph was plotted. After all, concentration of unknown metal found by graph.

2.3.3.4.3. Determination of metal content by AAS: The concentration of metal in 9 blood samples (BS1-BS9) was determined by using Varian 7000- GF Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry.

And ten blood samples (BS10-BS19) was determined by using 210 VGP Flame Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry [13] at lamda max of each metal as shown in table (2-1).

Table (2-1) at lamda max of metals

Metal	Wave length (nm)
Cd	228.8
Hg	253.7
Pb	217.0
Mn	279.5
Cu	324.8
Ni	232.0

The most common age groups participating in this study were the age group 21-30 and 31 – 40 years 30.4% and 27.5%, respectively, followed by more than 40 years 22% and less than 20 years 20.1%.

2.3.2.1. Preparation of standard solutions for AAS:

Standard calibration curve was constructed after recording the absorbance of standard solution prepared as follow: 10 ml were taken from the standard stock solution of each metal (1 mg/ml) and completed to 100 ml with distilled water. From this solutions 3 volumes were taken for each metal and completed to 100 ml with distilled water. The absorbance of the last 3 solutions was recorded and standard calibration curve was drawn and used for determination of the metal content in the samples under study [12].

3. RESULTS:

3.1. Statistical analysis : The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 26) was used to analyze the data, in this study p-value of 0 .05 was considered statistically significant. Frequency and percentage, to identify the personal data and ‘Knowledge of CLABSI Prevention. mean and standard deviation for behavior on prevention of CLABSI.

Table (3.1): Frequency distribution of participant age groups

Participant age	Frequency	Percent
Less than 20	63	20.1
21 to 30	95	30.4
31 to 40	86	27.5
More than 40	69	22.0
Total	313	100.0

Table (3.2) do you use hair dye?

Do you use hair dye?	Frequency	Percent
no	164	52.4
Sometimes	127	40.6
Yes, a lot	22	7.0
Total	313	100.0

About 47.6% of the study participant used hair dye, and 52.4% not used It , table 3.2

Table (3.3) The length of time since using hair dye

How long have you been using hair dye?	Frequency	Percent
A year - two years	33	10.5
Three - 5 years	45	14.4
Six - 8 years	25	8.0
More than 10 years	38	12.1
Do not use	172	55.0
Total	313	100.0

14.4 % used hair dye 3- 5 years, while 55% not used it and 12.1 % used for more than 10 years.

Table (3.4) Have you complained of any symptoms when you use hair dye?

Symptoms when using hair dye	Frequency	Percent
Yes	22	7.0
No	135	43.1
Do not use	156	49.8
Total	313	100.0

Table (3.5) Complaint after hair dyeing?

Complaints after dying hair	Frequency	Percent
Headache	22	7.0
A change in vision	2	.6
Irritation to the skin of the head	12	3.8
Hair loss	53	16.9
Nausea	1	.3
Swelling of the face	1	.3
Feeling of asphyxia	3	1.0
Don't use	219	70.0
Total	313	100.0

Figure (3.1) Complains after hair dyeing

4. DISCUSSION

Results showed that there were many factors that lead to gray hair: a hereditary factor, advancing age, anxiety, and stress. The use of individual creams and genetic factors. About half of the study participants used hair dye three to five years; they preferred black, brown, and Karkadawi colors for hair dye and practiced applying dye to hair mostly annually and often more than twice a year and monthly. Few of the participants complained of symptoms when they used hair dye like tonsillitis, general skin itching, runny nose, hair loss and brittleness, headache, itching, itchy scalp, headache, eye pain, and sinusitis, vertigo in the head, allergy and swelling above the eyebrow. The complaint after hair dyeing included hair loss, headache, irritation to the skin of the head, a change in vision, feeling of asphyxia, nausea. The majority of participants used dye to draw on skin. They used Tancho (Bigin) m drawing on the skin, Soft Color, black henna godrij (shata shata), Pakistani henna paste, and Gulf. Most of them used dye to draw on skin more than 10 years, while few from one to two years; they suffer from sensitivity (redness, swelling, itching) when using the dye to draw on their skin. The fast majority of participants' beauty purposes motivated them to use the dye for drawing on the skin. And they practice drawing dye for themselves at least once every three months and the others, the participants prefer natural henna and dyes for skin. There were many reasons for preferring dyeing: quick and can perform more beautiful shapes with it, can draw more beautiful shapes with it. They used dye and drawing during the first months of pregnancy. Many analytical atomic spectrometry methods are available for element determination, including flame atomic absorption spectrometry (FAAS), graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry (GF-AAS), flame atomic emission spectrometry (FAES), have been used for many years for the determination of elements since they meet the needs required in analytical applications. Atomic absorption spectrometry (FAAS), graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry (GF-AAS), were used in this study for the analysis of seven heavy metals (Cd, Pb, Mn, Cu, and Ni) in hair dyes due to its high sensitivity, low detection limit, and minimal analyte loss of interest during digestion processes in the conventional method of (AAS) to evaluate the risks that such cosmetics may pose to consumers. The concentration of heavy metals (Pb, Cr, Cd, Ni, and Cu) was determined using an atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS). Results of the current study showed the concentration of heavy metals in ppm in hair dye determined by flame AAS: in Tancho Hg (ppm) and Ni (ppm) recorded 0.0079700, 1.6990 respectively; in Godreg Hg (ppm), Mn (ppm), Ni (ppm) recorded 0.0255000, 19.4340 and 2.2985, respectively; in Soft colour Cu (ppm), Pb (ppm), Mn (ppm), Ni (ppm), recorded 4.7210, 2.5100, 163.4085, and 6.0960. Cu (ppm), Pb (ppm), Mn (ppm) and Ni In Garnai Hg (ppm), Mn (ppm), recorded 0.9288271, 13.6331 respectively. In Amira (ppm), recorded 3.0961, 17.4756, 294.8043 and 0.7911 respectively. In Henna potion Pakistani, Cd (ppm), Pb (ppm), Mn (ppm), recorded 0.1234, 7.9927, 6.4085 respectively. This is smaller to the study published in 2015 [14], concentration levels of some metals in various hair dye brand products sold at local shops in different locations in Iraq were determined, including Pb, Cd, iron (Fe), and copper (Cu). The selected toxic heavy metal concentrations were determined by flame atomic absorption spectrophotometer. Results of samples concentration revealed ranges of 0.41-0.91 ppm for Pb, 0.26-0.31 ppm for Cu, and 0.11-0.16 ppm for Cd. Hair dyes are regulated in the commercial marketplace and, as new toxicity data is generated for some hair dyes and health risks are

discovered, some of these hair dyes are being legally restricted from the cosmetic marketplace [15]. most concentrated of heavy metals and elements in blood samples of participants trace by GF AAS was in Pb and Cu which recorded 0.036, 0.358. The mean of concentration of LEAD in blood samples by FLAME AAS and GF AAS was 0.673, 0.04 consecutive. These are differ from Fariba Khalili et al. (Tehran, 2019) studied health risk assessment of dermal exposure to some heavy metals present in hair dyes [16], results indicated the average concentrations of Cu, and Pb as 61.32, and 185.34 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, respectively.

Amartey and Akwasi Bonsu Asumadu-Sakyi et al. [17], published a study for determination of heavy metals concentration in Hair Pomades on the Ghanaian Market Using Atomic Absorption Spectrometry Technique. Hair pomade samples collected from female students at the University of Ghana campus were analysed for heavy metal content using atomic absorption spectrometry technique. The concentrations were compared with available data on internationally acceptable maximum limits for these elements and their possible health implications on the consumer public. All the samples recorded significant levels for most of the elements of interest except Cr concentrations which were below detection ($<0.001 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$) for each of the samples analysed. The mean and standard deviation concentrations for the elements in mg/kg are as follows: Ca (421.055 Amartey and The current study is smaller to Akwasi Bonsu Asumadu-Sakyi et al. [17], for determination of heavy metals concentration in Hair Pomades on the Ghanaian Market Using Atomic Absorption Spectrometry Technique. Hair pomade samples collected from female students at the University of Ghana campus were analysed for heavy metal content using atomic absorption spectrometry technique. All the samples recorded significant levels for most of the elements of interest except Cr concentrations which were below detection ($<0.001 \text{ mg}/\text{kg}$) for each of the samples analysed. The mean and standard deviation concentrations for the elements in mg/kg are as follows: Ca (421.055), Co (16.036 ± 5.479), Cu (3.758), Mn (9.800), Cd (5.697), Ni (11.274) and Pb (8.269), Cu (3.758), and Pb (8.269). Elements such as Pb pass through the skin layers to blood vessels and are transported into various organs where they are accumulated and exert toxic effects [18].

Heavy metals are present in our environment, and it is therefore difficult to avoid their presence and impact on the human organism. It is known that heavy metals can be found in many cosmetic products, one of these is hair colors, where they can enter the body through the skin and root of the hair. In this way, if they are in high concentrations in the body, they can cause various health problems. It is therefore more important to determine the content of heavy metals (Cd, Pb, Mn, Cu and Ni) in hair dyes by using different types made by different manufacturers [19]. Health Canada has taken the initiative and implemented a few measures to control heavy metal concentration in cosmetics and determined the maximum acceptable limits i.e. Lead (10 ppm), Arsenic (3 ppm), Mercury (3 ppm), Cadmium (3 ppm) and Antimony (5 ppm). Cosmetic and hair dye has been one of the pollution resources of heavy metals [2].

In current study the limit of detection of AAs for metals and wave length Pb, Ni, Mn, Cu and Cd recorded 0.20, 0.13, 0.05, 0.04 and 0.01 LOD (mg/l). This results differ from Majda Benabbes and M Alami Chentoufi et al. (2021) reported concentration determination of Lead (Pb) and Cadmium (Cd) in sixteen locally marketed synthetic and natural Hair Dyes in Morocco using differential pulse polarography, employing mineralization with nitric acid and hydrogen peroxide [20]. The concentrations of the two metals in the different hair dyes samples ranged from LOD to 3617.02 ppm for Pb and from LOD to 459.57 ppm for Cd (both concentrations were above acceptable levels). Dyeing hair can change the content of heavy metals in hair, but the degree of effect is different for different element [3]. Symptoms of participants in blood samples by GF AAS, were Phlegm like sedation, Sinsitus eyes, Redness Mist and Tears Mist, Disease after dye drawing working were Sinsitus, Hypertension+ cholestrol, Symptoms of participants in blood samples by FLAME were AAHeadache Sneezing when Preparation, Allergy at night in eyes, Allergy with HD-D m Increase flu if she had, Allergy in period of using and whitening cream. Disease after dye drawing working were Hypertension, Sinsitus+Allergy, Allergy+Thyrodism+ Prolactine, Allergy amsd Feeling in throat. These results differ from researchers believed that hair dye could cause cancer, especially in women who used the darker colors. In fact, some studies even showed that using hair dye repeatedly could increase the risk of non-Hodgkin's lymphoma and multiple myeloma [21]. Elements such as Ni, and Cr are accumulated in the stratum corneum and may cause allergic contact dermatitis [22]

5. CONCLUSION

The current study concluded that: There is presence of lead, copper, chromium, nickel and cadmium in all the hair dye samples analyzed. The pure mineral dyes have higher concentrations of the heavy metals than the synthetic dyes studied. Long term and the frequency of usage of these products polluted with such heavy metals should be avoided. These may cause slow release of these

metals into the human body and may pose a serious health risk to their users. Regulatory agencies saddled with maintaining standard of products should regularly monitor these products for long-term health benefits of the users. Heavy metals of Cd, Pb, Cu, Hg, Cr and Ni, were found in all hair dye samples tested. Heavy metals in blood samples of participants cause many symptoms and disease after using hair dyes and skin drawing. The most concentrated heavy metals and trace elements of (Pb, Cd, Mn, Hg, Cu and Ni) in blood samples of participants were tested. Results clarified that the high concentration represented for LEAD in blood samples by FLAME AAS and GF AAS.

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